

THE ROLE OF LABOR RESOURCES IN THE PROCESS OF ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT.

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the influence of labor resources that affects the activities of the enterprise. Improving the quality of labor resources contributes to the growth of the socio-economic efficiency of the enterprise.*

Keywords: *labor resources, enterprise, quality labor resources, socio-economic efficiency.*

Introduction.

With the development of market relations in the production system of an enterprise, labor resources become the most important element in ensuring the production of products, their sales and the implementation of other functions of the enterprise, the main one of which is the enterprise management function. Consequently, the effective functioning of an enterprise is impossible without choosing the goals for the formation and use of labor resources in accordance with the needs of the enterprise's production system and solving the problem of optimal resource allocation. Since there can be many problems, they require their joint effective solution.

In this regard, it seems appropriate to consider, first of all, the very concept of “enterprise labor resources” from the standpoint of the essential features of this economic category. The category of enterprise labor resources as an economic category reflects the entire system of economic, social and interpersonal relations that take place in an enterprise in market conditions.

The transition of the country's economy to market relations has caused the need to rethink and clarify the main categories of the theory of labor relations, such as : labor resources, labor potential, labor force, among which the leading place belongs to the category of “labor resources”. It is characteristic that some economists believed that with the transition to market relations, the category “labor resources” may lose its former meaning, but, as research shows, the interest of prominent academic economists in the use of this category in practical activities is increasing.

It is used not only in relation to a part of the country's population that has a certain set of abilities, but also as a resource (factor) for the production of products at an enterprise.

In modern science, the concepts of “employee labor potential” and “human capital” are used. As noted by Genkin B.M. “The labor potential of an employee is a set of human characteristics that arise as a result of material and spiritual investments in him: intelligence, creativity, health, education, professionalism, morality, activity, organization” [17]

Currently, the efficiency of an enterprise largely depends on labor resources. Since the activities of any enterprise directly depend on the competent use and effective management of personnel, we can conclude that staffing is one of the main resources of the enterprise. At the present stage of economic development, much attention is paid to the problem of increasing the socio-economic efficiency of an enterprise. It helps ensure the accuracy and clarity of the company's work. Currently, the development of the economy of Uzbekistan involves many approaches that ensure an increase in both the social and economic efficiency of the enterprise. These include the formation of high-quality labor resources. This is explained by the fact that for Uzbekistan, it is necessary to form high-quality labor resources, which, in turn, contribute to increasing the competitiveness of goods, works, and services. According to academician K.Kh. Abdurakhmanov, “distance relationships” between employer and employees are an integral part

of the process of decentralization of labor in time and space. It also serves to form a flexible virtual labor market” [2, p. 325].

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays special attention to the issues of promoting employment and creating working conditions. The country has adopted the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 [1] and has set the goal of creating new jobs in the country, increasing incomes of the population, and thereby reducing poverty by at least two times by the end of 2026, which is directly related to the need to activate the labor market and ensure employment

The quality of labor resources affects the development process of the enterprise and has a beneficial effect on increasing the socio-economic efficiency of its activities. The productive potential of labor resources includes not only the psychological and physical qualities of the company’s employees, but also the parameters which determine the degree of their performance, as well as suitability to perform assigned tasks in the process of work. Such parameters include the level of education (general and special), production work experience, which is accumulated and passed on from generation to generation, and cultural norms of behavior of enterprise employees.

The production of goods and services largely depends on the enterprise's supply of labor resources and their effective use. During the analysis of labor resources, the following is determined:

- provision of the enterprise with personnel in terms of number, composition, skill level and structure;
- correspondence between the professional composition of the enterprise and the level of qualifications;
- dynamics of movement of labor resources;
- use of working time.

Part of the country's labor resources is the labor resources of the enterprise. From the point of view of the scientific category, labor resources include able-bodied citizens who, thanks to their intellectual and psychophysiological characteristics, are able to perform work to produce material services or goods and contribute to the growth of the socio-economic efficiency of the enterprise. These resources include all people employed in the economy, as well as those who are not employed in it, but can carry out labor activities. In accordance with statistical data, it is possible to present a picture of the economically active population of the country

/ Employment rate in %/

The ratio of the number of employed population to the working age population

Regions	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Republic of Uzbekistan	67,1	67,7	68,2	68,7	69,2	67,4	68,1	66,0	67,0	67,2
Republic of Karakalpakstan		57,7	57,9	58,1	58,1	58,3	62,9	62,9	62,0	61,1
Andijan	69,9	70,8	71,5	72,3	73,0	69,6	70,1	66,5	68,2	69,5
Bukhara	74,4	74,0	73,4	72,9	72,5	70,7	69,3	68,3	67,2	67,2
Jizzakh	56,5	57,3	58,1	59,1	60,0	61,6	67,1	66,2	67,5	66,2
Kashkadarya	61,8	2,5	63,3	64,3	65,4	64,8	63,9	60,9	62,2	61,9
Navoi	74,1	73,6	73,2	72,8	72,4	69,2	69,5	66,8	68,3	67,7

Namangan	58,1	59,3	60,5	61,9	63,4	63,8	66,4	65,0	65,5	64,8
Samarkand	65,4	66,5	67,6	68,7	69,7	66,3	65,3	63,2	63,7	64,7
Surkhandarya	62,7	63,4	64,3	65,4	66,6	65,2	67,0	63,9	64,5	64,2
Syrdarya	72,5	72,9	72,2	71,7	71,1	70,5	68,9	64,8	64,5	64,0
Tashkent	74,0	75,1	75,3	75,4	75,2	71,4	71,4	68,2	72,4	71,0
Fergana	68,3	68,8	69,1	69,6	69,9	66,0	67,5	65,1	66,2	67,1
Khorezm	64,3	65,0	65,6	66,3	66,9	64,6	66,1	63,7	64,0	64,7
Tashkent city	80,7	80,9	81,1	81,0	80,8	77,5	80,1	81,7	81,3	82,5

According to the Statistics Agency, in 2023 the number of economically active population of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 15,071.3 thousand people, which is 90.6 thousand people more than the corresponding period of the previous year. The share of the economically active population is 77.3% of all labor resources of our countries.

The role of labor resources in the activities of the enterprise

The following factors are used:

- goal setting and task setting;
- strategy, tactics for achieving goals;
- making decisions and taking necessary actions;
- production of products for consumers;
- development of activities.

Labor resources are one of the components of the capital of an economic entity. The labor capital of enterprises is expressed by the labor of highly qualified workers, the number of which is determined by the technology used. As the level of technology increases, the requirements for labor capital increase.

Entrepreneurial capital is determined by such indicators as entrepreneurship, innovation, ability to organize and take risks, a sense of economy, energy intensity and some others. These personality traits are necessary for effective management and quality business. At the same time, the quality of entrepreneurial abilities can be determined after assessing the effectiveness of the use of entrepreneurial capital and the stability of enterprise development

In the current period of economic development, when all types of competition in the domestic and international markets have significantly intensified, a situation has arisen in which only organizations that have serious competitive advantages in comparison with business entities that produce similar products or perform work are able to reach a high level of commercial activity, provide services. One of the main advantages that the company has is the level of professional training of its workforce. Such workers have the knowledge, skills and abilities to perform their job functions efficiently.

Conclusion.

Thus, we can conclude that the provision of an enterprise with labor resources and their rational use are key factors for the successful operation of an enterprise in modern economic conditions. Therefore great importance should be given to the analysis of the use of labor resources at the enterprise

Summarizing a of the above, it is important to note that the labor force is the population that, due to health and age, can work. At the same time, people who are employed in one enterprise are considered the labor resources of this enterprise. It is important to pay special attention to working with them, otherwise it will not be possible to build a successful business, because it is people who produce the product. Consequently, in order to eliminate existing negative trends in

relation to the development of labor resources, a system of measures should be introduced, the most important element of which at present should be improving the quality of labor resources

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